

ENERGY-SAVING CONTROL SCHEME OF ELECTRICAL CONTROL OF HORIZONTAL LAMINATING MACHINE

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Закрытый электропривод с частотно-параметрическим управлением. На этом принципе построено множество частотно-управляемых асинхронных электрических цепей. Регулировка скорости осуществляется по следующему принципу регулировки, с использованием координат РС ПИ-регулятора скорости, регулятора интенсивности ЗИ и блока ограничителя тока БО.

ANNOTATION

Closed electric drive with frequency parametric control. Using this principle, many frequency-controlled asynchronous electric circuits have been built. Speed adjustment is carried out according to the following adjustment principle, using coordinates RS speed PI-regulator, intensity controller ZI and current limiter BO block

Frequency from the converters used closed electricity procedures

In general, the frequency control of the motor using frequency converters can be implemented in three options:

- parametric control, in this case, the controlling effect on the motor is the

frequency and the influencing value of the voltage transmitted to the motor;

- frequency-current control, in this case, the control effect on the motor is the frequency and the effective value of the motor current;
- vector control. Such control is related to the control of the instantaneous values of the supply voltage and currents in order to form the electromagnetic moment of the electric motor.

Closed circuit with parametric control. Many frequency-controlled asynchronous electric drives are built using this principle. Due to the use of various reverse connections and functional blocks, fixed (fixed) operating sections of the mechanical characteristics of the engine are formed, current and torque are limited, and the required ratios of controlled frequency and voltage are provided for quality control of its speed. A generalized scheme of such an electrical circuit It is presented in Figure 1.

A frequency converter with a constant current circuit is used as a power converter. A constant current loop frequency converter is composed of an uncontrolled rectifier and a voltage inverter, the inverter is composed of six power modules consisting of transistors and diodes. A filter is connected between the rectifier and the inverter, the filter is composed of a reactor L and a capacitor C. The filter provides smoothing of the output voltage of the rectifier and ensures the necessary circulation of reactive energy in the power part of the circuit.

Picture 1 . Frequency in management asynchronous electricity don't drive scheme

, provides the required speed and acceleration of the engine with the help of the f_u signal in the stationary and transient modes of the electric drive .

Limitation of the motor stator current and torque is carried out by the current regulator RT; when the motor stator current is less than I_m , the signal at the RT output is zero, and the control circuit provides the set speed holding mode. When the motor stator current increases from I_m , the signal at the RT output increases sharply, so the signal at the output of the adder S_1 also decreases sharply. This leads to a decrease in the frequency and voltage in the motor stator, and at the same time leads to a limitation of the motor stator current and torque.

In order to reduce the effect of the voltage drop in the stator circuit on the magnitude of the motor magnetic current, and thus to reduce its effect on the torque, the circuit (so-called IR-compensation) provides a positive feedback on the current. The feedback signal is fed to the input of the adder S_2 . As the motor load increases, its current increases and the U_u signal increases, due to which the output voltage of the converter increases and, therefore, the voltage drop in the stator winding is compensated.

In modern electrical systems of this type, the implementation (preparation) of the control blocks of the circuit is carried out using microprocessor circuits (Fig. 2-a), and the adjustment of their parameters and characteristics is done by programming. The mechanical characteristics of the engine obtained at different signals of the speeds specified in this scheme are shown in Fig. 2- b.

Frequency-current control of an asynchronous motor. The circuit diagram is shown in Figure 2 . Thyristors VS1 – VS6 form the controlled rectifier UV circuit, and thyristors VS7 – VS12 form the current autonomous inverter AIT.

Between these blocks, a reactor L with a large inductance is connected, which gives the inverter the characteristic of a current source. $S1 - S6$ capacitors $VD1 - VD6$ together with thyristors $VS7 - VS12$ form artificial switching circuits. Other elements of the circuit are designed for: SUV and SUI – circuits controlling rectifier and inverter thyristors; RT, DT – adjuster (regulator) and stator current sensor, respectively; DS – speed sensor; UO – amplifier-limiter (usilitel-ogranichitel); FP – functional modifier. The scheme works as follows.

Picture 2 . Frequent managed asynchronous electricity don't drive scheme

The duty signal U_{zs} determines the switching frequency of the inverter thyristors and, at the same time, the frequency of the motor stator current M . After the subtraction of the feedback signal of the speed U_{ω} from the signal U_{zs} , the signal U_b is generated, this signal is proportional to the relative frequency of the rotor $b = f_2 / f_{1nom}$ (the value b is also called the absolute slip of the engine) . This quantity is related to engine slip s as follows: $b = a s$, where $a = f_1 / f_{1nom}$.

The U_b signal passes through UO and enters the SUI input together with the U_{ω} signal. Frequency at the inverter output $U_{\omega s} = U_{\omega} + U_b$; The SUI is configured so that when the UO is operating in the linear zone, the frequency at the output of the inverter is constant and does not depend on the load. In this case,

the engine will have fixed (fixed) mechanical characteristics.

It is also the signal for the current rectifier circuit after the β signal passes through the FP. Since this signal is proportional to the absolute slip, the motor current will be proportional to it at all frequencies.

In case of sharp changes in the duty signal or small loads of the motor, UO enters the limit zone of its output signal U_b signal (invariance), thereby limiting the duty to the specified level required for the current. The engine will work at any speed with constant values of absolute slip, that is, the mechanical characteristics will remain absolutely "soft". As a result, the engine will have characteristics similar to those shown in Figure 2-b .

The scheme ensures the implementation of motor braking with energy recuperation (giving) to the grid, for which the inverter is switched to the rectification mode, and the rectifier is switched to the current inverter mode.

The equation of electromagnetic torque of an induction motor can have different written forms. These forms depend on the variables used in these equations and the coordinate system that represents them. When building a vector control system, it is more convenient to express the processes in the engine in the X – Y coordinate system, where the rotor's flow resistance PS and its speed overlap in the direction of the X axis. In this case, the equation of the electromagnetic moment of a three-phase asynchronous motor will have the following form:

$$M = \frac{3pL_{12} \cdot \Psi_2 \cdot i_{1v}}{2L_2}$$

where p — the number of motor pole pairs; L_{12} — mutual inductance between the stator and the rotor; i_{1u} — component of the stator current along the Y axis;

L_2 — total inductance of the rotor.

The component of the stator current i_{1x} is the flexibility of the rotor current

along the X axis

PS , in which, considering the above formula, it is determined that by adjusting i_{1x} and i_{1u} , it is possible to ensure the formation of engine torque. The component i_{1x} can be seen as the magnetizing reactive component of the motor stator current, while i_{1u} is the active component that generates the motor torque.

The above equation is exactly similar in form to the DC motor torque formula. In it, PS_2 represents the DC motor magnetic flux, and i_{1u} represents its armature current.

3 . Scheme of asynchronous electric drive with current vector control.

4 shows the principle of vector control scheme construction . M asynchronous motor, on the shaft of which a speed sensor DS (tachogenerator) is installed, is fed from a PCH frequency converter. Torque adjustment RT_w active I_w and RT_μ reactive I_μ is aligned with the constituents of μ . The values of these variables are obtained indirectly using the asynchronous motor model "Model AD". Phase currents I_A, I_V, I_S , phase voltages U_A, U_V , Signals U_S and engine angular velocity ω are given. The engine model provides information about the components of the engine slip s and I_w, I_μ currents.

Speed adjustment is carried out according to the principle of follow-up adjustment, using coordinates RS speed PI-regulator, intensity controller ZI and current limiter BO block. PCH control three-phase U_A, U_V , It is carried out with

a system of s voltages. The system of three-phase voltages is formed by the PK coordinate converter. It is formed on the basis of the signals of the RT_w and RT_μ tuners and on the basis of the signal proportional to the frequency f_1 .

Vector adjustment of the torque of the induction motor ensures that it is precisely maintained in the entire range of speed control. to this can be added the operation of the electric drive in the mode of operation and its operation at very low "creep" speeds, which shows that it is distinguished above the parametric (scalar) adjustment.

STA-S2 series frequency converters _ vector type small are universal size converters . them the majority engineering their work solution in reaching , short connected rotor general industry asynchronous of an electric motor rotation frequency to correct done increase if necessary use can (machine equipment electro transporters , conveyors , mixers , pumps , fans __ and etc ...).

Frequency converter _ main functional options : Fig. 4

- management vector mode , U/f volt-frequency characteristic as long as possible management ;
- automatic setup mode ;
- working of the engine to the speed adjustment ;
- S- shaped of speed increase and of the engine braking ;
- frequency of the converter programmed mode ;
- into installed _ high frequency PID- regulator ;
- integrated analog 0-10 V / 4-20 mA output ;
- integrated interface RS-485 MODBUS RTU
- high in daja again loading feature _

- small massagabarit in the indicators high FIK;
- many p numerous protection functions .

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